

Students' Motivation In Speaking English Using Tiktok

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Abstract: At present, technology is rapidly advancing, which is undoubtedly a positive development that we should harness. Social media is one of the outcomes of this technological progress. Nowadays, the use of social media goes beyond being merely a means of communication; it has been utilized in various sectors such as the economy, religion, tourism, and education. One of the relatively recent additions to the realm of social media is TikTok. This research aims to explore how students are motivated in learning speaking skills using TikTok. A qualitative descriptive approach was chosen for this study. A motivation questionnaire was employed to identify the motivational aspects that emerge, as well as the TikTok features that contribute to speaking skill acquisition. Additionally, semi-structured interviews were conducted to gain deeper insights. This research involved a class at SMA N Jatirogo. The findings of this study indicate that TikTok has a positive impact on enhancing student motivation. Motivation is evident in various aspects, such as enjoyment, challenges, increased curiosity, and more. However, there are still some aspects that need further optimization and improvement in using TikTok for speaking skill development, including monitoring TikTok usage and certain social aspects that may not be as impactful as desired. This research can be valuable for prospective teachers and educators who intend to use TikTok as a tool for teaching the English language.

INTRODUCTION

The four skills that make up English are as follows: They're paying attention, conversing, and listening to each other. Reading and writing are two of my favorite activities. Speaking has become more and more crucial in recent years. As a technique of communication in daily life in second/foreign language contexts life. O'Malley and Pierce are in favor of it (1996, p.57). On the other side based on PS Rao (2019)

communication skills are critical in today's society, and mastery of these skills is required to achieve success in one's chosen career. To communicate effectively in this global environment, speaking is the most critical of the four language skills.

Teachers should establish a positive learning environment for students so that they are pleased, interested, and motivated to study English. The desire to learn the language could be boosted if creating favorable media, favorable surroundings, and creative activities. Teachers, according to Nunan (1999), should assist their students by developing techniques to handle all types of communication so that all students have equal and fair opportunities to improve their interpersonal speaking skills.

Several variables influence how well English is learned and taught in schools. One of them is how English is taught and learned, particularly speaking techniques, through methods and media. With the right methods and media, it can increase the ability and confidence level of students in speaking English. This must be followed by projecting to students to gauge how well they are learning.

The new curriculum and technology advancements of today force teachers to be more inventive in their selection of the best media for the teaching and learning process. Social Media is one of the media that teachers can use to increase learning activities. Based on the aim of social media, there were four main purposes for using social media applications, which are entertainment, socialization, in formativeness, and academic Yang (2020). Social media has the potential to be a

powerful educational tool Almodiel (2017). Social media is increasingly widely used by individuals in this digital age and serves a variety of purposes, one of which is serving as a tool for language learning.

According to the Republic of Indonesia's No. 22 of 2006 Regulation on the Content issued by the Minister of Education (PERMENDIKNAS). Language is essential for the growth of the mind, the social world, and the emotional world. encourage students and succeed in learning all subjects, as stated in Putra et al., (2017) There are several learning resources that we can take from social media platforms such as easy understanding explanations, funny games, and song challenges that we can use to trigger students' speaking ability.

TikTok is one of the social media Which is serving variative ways to improve learning media. On the other hand, meaningful teaching is needed to give students motivation during learning English. It is also essential to consider what students need from their condition. TikTok can be used as an effective learning tool because 1) it satisfies students' learning needs; 2) it piques their curiosity due to its novelty and has a variety of features that can be incorporated into learning; and 3) it embodies the characteristics of students from the millennial generation, who are attached and close to the digital world, especially gadgets, and who are developing maturity and experience Aji (2018).

There are several studies conducted in the last few years related to social media, especially TikTok. Aji (2018) in the research of TikTok, in combination with appropriate methods and technology, can be used as an interactive learning media in the study of the Indonesian language and culture. In the other research about TikTok in EFL classrooms. The study's findings indicated that using English Tik Tok teaching videos in EFL classroom instruction could increase students' English learning

motivation and spark their learning interests. Tik Tok integration in the EFL classroom could improve their classroom teaching activities while also broadening their English knowledge Yang (2020).

Anggi, Naura, and Riska said that Many of the respondents use TikTok for learning because it offers numerous advantages, including recommendations, tips and tricks, advantages, and the ability to increase knowledge and conduct business. Some respondents do not use TikTok, but they are aware of what TikTok is and what can be done in this TikTok app, among other things. They also found the problem related to the use of TikTok as media for teaching pronunciation. Pronunciation is one of the speaking aspects which is important to inspect.

The purpose of conducting this was to investigate the type of motivation that appear. Moreover, this study is not only going to see students' motivation toward the implementation of TikTok. Therefore, the researcher will research "Student Motivation in Learning Speaking English TikTok at SMA N Jatirogo.

The definition and implementation of the construct of motivation in the classroom have proven to be one of the more challenging issues in second language learning and teaching. On the one hand, it's a simple catchphrase that offers teachers a straightforward solution to the enigma of language acquisition. The difference lies in motivation Brown (2001). Those statements have been supported by Cheng and Dornyei (2007). They asserted that students with strong motivation would more readily learn more in a particular foreign language than would smarter individuals with low motivation. The

student's strong motivation is hence equally as crucial as their level of comprehension. Juniar (2016) also gave a strong opinion that it was hard to learn English with poor motivation.

In case to make student motivation boost, Dornyei (2001) states that Teachers can use interactive learning activities in the classroom to boost motivation among language learners, but empirical research is still needed to determine the true benefit of these techniques.

Speaking

Speaking, according to Ladouse in Nunan (1991: 23), is an activity that is used to explain something to someone or to report something. Meanwhile, Tarigan (1990: 8) defines "speaking" as "ways of communicating that affect our daily lives." This means that speaking is a form of communication that can have an impact on someone's life.

Based on the preceding explanation, the writer concludes that speaking is a way to express what we feel, which is then manifested in the form of spoken language processes between two or more people

Social Media

Social networks have firmly established themselves in contemporary culture. Through the use of platforms like Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn, online gaming environments, and others, people have incorporated these networks into their daily lives. Kids who use social networking become more peer-based. Online peer learning is encouraged among young people. They converse with one another and exchange opinions. They have a stronger motivation to learn from one another than

from adults. Social media is a tool to boost users' capacity to share, collaborate with other users, and take activities outside the institutional and organizational structure, according to Shirky in Azka (2019). Meike and Young view social media as a relationship between communication, which entails sharing amongst people, and public media to share with anybody in Nasrullah (2016). The use of social media could not separate from positive and negative aspects it should be considered the effect on the user. Social media is a tool to boost users' capacity to share, collaborate with other users, and take activities outside the institutional and organizational structure, according to Shirky in Azka (2019).

Social Media nowadays is already used in education needs. By utilizing social media, some of our teachers have profited from instructing in a relaxed but productive setting. Due to the subject requirements, students may use eLearn's Blog, Forum, or Wiki capabilities as well as YouTube for subject-related content. They may also use Facebook or other social media sites for their learning activities. According to Fitri (2017), the development of technology will negatively affect several socio-cultural factors, such as the following.

- a. The deterioration of social norms, particularly among youths and students
- b. Growing teenage misbehavior among teenagers and lax communal traditions.
- c. Modified social behavior. With the overwhelming use of technology in the environment each family member's interpersonal style has evolved as a result of the family.

TikTok

Launched in 2017, TikTok had reached more than 150 countries worldwide as of January 2020, with over 400 million DAU (Daily Active User). TikTok received nearly 315 million downloads from the App Store and Google Play in the first quarter of 2020, bringing its total downloads to 2 billion, while the Chinese version received nearly 315 million downloads. According to Sensor Tower, a world-renowned app tracking company [Sensor, 2020], the version had 518 million users and 28.5 hours per person per month.

TikTok users are divided into three groups: content creators, content browsers, and learner creators. TikTok has an easy-to-use interface for creating, editing, and sharing short videos; users can also comment on and share content with the TikTok community at large. TikTok videos can last anywhere from a few seconds to 60 seconds. Originally, videos could only be 15 seconds long, but TikTok now allows users to loop a 15-second loop four times to create a 60-second video. The application is currently testing a new feature that allows users to upload videos up to three minutes long. This modification may have a significant impact on how users interact with the application (AA, Comendulli, 2020). TikTok as one part of social media also has a purpose. As Gupta and Bashir state in cities of (Yang,2020) The main reasons for using social media applications were for entertainment, socialization, information, and academic purposes. In the case of academic purposes especially in English learning, TikTok serves several supportive contents that teachers can use as a medium in learning activities.

METHODOLOGY

This study uses a mixed method which combines qualitative and quantitative data in one study in order to gain a more complete and in-depth understanding of a phenomenon (Creswell, 2014). The research design used in this study is categorized as survey research. The objective of the researcher is to comprehend real-life behavior by gathering survey data for analysis. A motivation questionnaire was employed to identify the motivational aspects that emerge, as well as the TikTok features that contribute to speaking skill acquisition. Additionally, semi-structured interviews were conducted to gain deeper insights.

FINDING AND DISCUSSION

The researcher used two instruments, which are questionnaires and interviews, to address the first research questions. The Likert scale used in this survey has the following responses: SA (Strongly Agree), A (Agree), N (Neutral), D (Disagree), and SD (Strongly Disagree). After getting information from the interview, the researcher conducted an interview to dig deeper into the data that had been obtained so that the results of a deeper analysis could be obtained.

Dealing with whether or how using TikTok helped students concentrate. According to the data gathered, 8,33% of respondents strongly agree, 58,3% agree, 29,1% are neutral, and 4,16 percent disagree. According to the data above there are some students who agree that tiktok can motivate them to be more focused.

The element of fun and curiosity comes next. Regarding the pleasure factor, it was shown that 62.5% of respondents agreed, and 12.5% felt that they strongly agreed, that learning to speak English through tick tock was fun. While 25% of those surveyed gave a neutral response.

Tik Tok also had correlation to the students' activeness in the class. The data shows that TikTok does not help much in increasing activity in speaking english. There are only 33,3 % students that agree and 12,5% very agree. However, 20,8% of students disagree and the rest are neutral. From the result a huge percentage of respondents that disagree that TikTok are able to make them more active in speaking english. The result of Confidence is quite similar with the Social aspect which there 8,33% do not agree and 62,5% disagree. Then 20,8% agree and 8,33% strongly agree.

After getting data from respondents about what features are of interest, researchers will calculate and display data using and percentage. In addition, for each participant, they can choose more than one feature. Based data from the questionnaire shows that the tiktok feature that motivates students the most is the up to date feature with 90% of students choosing it. next followed by easy to use with 62.5%. then there is video sharing with 20.8% and 8.33% for duet. Last is 0% video editing.

According to the current questionnaire, it was indicated that the features of fun and curiosity had a favorable reaction, with 75% of respondents feeling joyful and 70.1% of respondents feeling intrigued. This demonstrates that the majority of students cite enjoyment and curiosity as the factors that have the greatest impact on motivating them.

The findings of interviews with particular information from all respondents, which show that they enjoy using TikTok as a tool for learning English, reinforce this. They think that TikTok will be helpful in making teaching and learning activities more entertaining when used to learn English. Triandi (2021) stated that creating an enjoyable learning atmosphere is crucial for students to learn effectively. Students can only learn well when they are in a pleasant environment, feeling safe and free from fear.

Additionally, they claimed that the duet component in tiktok increased their sense of challenge. However, there is still room for improvement in this duet feature. based on what the fourth student, who thought the challenge was inadequate, said. Besides that, the fourth student also tends to prefer learning through books compared to videos like TikTok. The third pupil felt challenged to become a TikTok celebrity, it was also discovered. This is due to the fact that generating material is now a job in the modern digital era and tiktok has become popular among young people. The rest of the respondents feel more challenged to use TikTok with existing challenges and duets.

For the aspect of curiosity, almost all students agree that curiosity increased except for the 6th student. He believes that the information on tiktok has little bearing on the content of the book. He nevertheless continues to use English materials outside of class time. This is due to how simple the English content in tiktok is to understand and apply. 83.3 percent of students responded that they agreed with this. The interview's findings also revealed that the six students thought the English content on Tiktok was simple to comprehend and use. The third student claimed

that TikTok has elements that make learning simple and that text in content makes it simpler to comprehend the subject matter. According to the 4th student, the material on tiktok is related to learning and can be applied directly, so this increases his motivation when learning using tiktok.

TikTok aids in independent English learning, and speaking English actively has an inverse relationship with that. Using tiktok, 80% of students were assisted in learning independently, whereas only 45.8% talked more actively. The fifth student believes that TikTok speaking exercises need to be repeated or should be practiced more frequently.

Because hearing alone won't help them get well. On the other hand, the third student felt more active speaking after using TikTok. the same as with students when students first feel more serious so they can improve speaking skills more. Self-confidence has detrimental effects, with 8% of pupils reporting higher self-confidence levels. The fifth student remarked that lack of practice made self-confidence less apparent when learning to utilize tiktok. He previously considered that there should be further follow-up regarding the material being taught on activity.

Independent learning is also one of the factors that influence one's focus. like the 6th student where he is more focused on learning to use TikTok himself. However, students 1,3,4 and 5 feel unable to focus using tiktok. This is caused because they are disturbed by the appearance of other content.

The researcher used student surveys and student interviews to address the second research issue. Interviews and study questionnaires shared many similarities. It means that in order to obtain more

information, the interview segment was added after the results of the questionnaires. The researcher cited five tiktok features on the questionnaire sheet, including duet, easy to use, up to date, video sharing, and video editing. Based on the results of the questionnaire it was found that several aspects had been selected by students. They believe that tiktok can increase their motivation to learn English speaking

The up to date feature is the feature with the highest gain. There are 22 students chosen up to date as the features that motivate students in learning speaking English using TikTok. The development of the times which resulted in the development of existing technology and information to be faster. This of course makes the current generation of children not want to be left behind with the others. We can get the information easily and it is in our hands. One of the media that can help obtain information is social media. This also supported by interview students' 6 said:

In another term, the second highest choices of the students were 15 students choosing easy to use. Tiktok offers a simple interface that gives users the freedom to select the topics they are and are not interested in, allowing users to control the type of material that is produced. In addition, TikTok offers user-friendly video material that is simple to grasp and use. The third student's viewpoint, "Yes, why because it's easy, right? supports this. The issue is that kids today prefer to open TikTok. "Is it simple, is that simple to find, huh?"

The results above show that being up to date is a feature that is popular and makes motivation to learn speaking English increase. Those

findings were quite similar to the variety of learning in Aji (2021), and Setiyadi (2021). This aspect makes it easy for students to access various types of learning content about speaking English easily.

CONCLUSION

After conducting this research, two conclusions were drawn. The first conclusion is that most students in XII grades science 4 of SMA N Jatirogo are motivated when teachers use TikTok as a medium for teaching speaking English. In addition, There are also several aspects that arise among others, starting from them feeling happy, challenged, their curiosity increased. Speaking English Material on TikTok is easy to understand and practice with material that is light and easy to understand, students can use TikTok as a learning medium with enjoyment. By using social media, students feel more comfortable and enjoy participating in learning speaking English.

However, there are some things that teachers need to pay attention to. the social aspect must be optimized. the use of various types of duet content involving students in groups needs to be conditioned. the focus aspect needs to be considered again because when using tiktok other videos may appear which might disturb students' concentration in learning. It is also worth noting for the sort of student learning. Students with an audio-kinesthetic learning style will be more motivated, whereas students with a visual learning style will be less driven. As a result, assignments or resources other than tiktok, such as reading books, should also be used.

For the second research question, TikTok features that determine students' motivation were up to date and easy to use. It was proved by most students that TikTok contents were up to date. it is relevant nowadays so make it closer to the student environment and need. They

also believe that TikTok was easy to use so make them easy to understand and apply the material easily.

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